

Experimental Study on the Effect of Using Preheated Fuel on Engine Performance and Emission

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Abstract: Because of urbanization, recycling scrap tires into energy has become more popular as a way to get rid of waste tires. Of the many techniques, pyrolysis seems feasible, attractive, and practical for producing goods like pyrolysis oil, which can be mixed with petroleum oils and used as an energy source. A mixture of tyre pyrolysis oil (TPO) and jatropa methyl ester (JME) was used as diesel engine fuel in a previous study. It was found that the JMETPO20 (JME80% + TPO20%) blend performed better than diesel operation but better than all other test blends. Additionally, it was reported that engines running on diesel performed better than those running on the JMETPO20 blend because of its higher viscosity. In this regard, an effort has been made to replace traditional diesel with the JMETPO20 blend at various preheating temperatures. A single-cylinder diesel engine with a rated output of 4.4 kW was used for the experiments, and the blend was preheated at three different temperatures: 50, 60, and 70°C. The investigations' findings were examined, contrasted with diesel, and reported in this study.

Keywords: Alternative fuel; Diesel engine; Performance; Preheating; Emission

1. Introduction

The global energy crisis has become a pressing issue, impacting economies, societies, and the environment. As fossil fuel reserves dwindle and climate change accelerates, the requirement for sustainable and innovative energy solutions has never been more critical [1]. The energy crisis is characterized by rising energy prices, supply shortages, and increased demand for energy resources. Factors contributing to this crisis include geopolitical tensions, natural disasters, and the ongoing effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, which have disrupted supply chains and energy production [2]. As countries strive to recover economically, the demand for energy continues to surge, leading to heightened competition for limited resources [3]. This is happening due to excessive usage of fossil fuels, the adverse effect of combustion of fossil fuel on human being and environment etc.

With respect to the energy crisis, many nations are pivoting towards renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, and geothermal power. These alternatives bid a sustainable solution to the energy demands of the future while reducing the adverse effects of climate change [4]. Technological advancements have made renewable energy

more accessible and cost-effective, with solar and wind energy becoming increasingly competitive with traditional fossil fuels. In addition to this, the revolutions in energy storage, such as batteries and pumped hydro storage, are talking the intermittence trials associated with renewable energy generation [5]. Figure 1 shows the reason for energy crisis.

The evolution to a maintainable energy future also involves enhancing energy efficiency and promoting conservation practices. Governments and organizations are executing policies and incentives to encourage energy-saving technologies and practices among consumers and businesses. Smart grids, energy-efficient appliances, and electric vehicles are just a few examples of how technology can play a pivotal role in reducing energy consumption and emissions. Moreover, the future of energy is likely to be characterized by decentralization [6]. Distributed energy resources, such as rooftop solar panels and community wind farms, empower individuals and local communities to generate their own energy[7]. This shift not only enhances energy security but also fosters resilience against supply disruptions and price volatility [8].

The energy crisis presents significant challenges, but it also offers an opportunity for transformative change. By embracing renewable energy, enhancing efficiency, and fostering decentralized energy systems, we can pave the way for a sustainable energy future. The path forward requires collaboration among governments, businesses, and individuals to innovate and invest in the technologies and practices that will define the energy landscape of tomorrow. The objective of the present work is to explore the possibilities of using biofuels as alternative to diesel fuels toward a more sustainable energy future.

Fig.1 Reason of energy crisis

2. Test fuels

The alternative fuel can be majorly classified as first-generation biofuels, second generation biofuels and third generation biofuels [9]. Biofuels have emerged as a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, offering a renewable source of energy that can help mitigate climate change and reduce greenhouse gas emissions [10]. Many studies explore the various types of biofuels, including their production methods, characteristics, and performance metrics, specifically focusing on brake thermal efficiency (BTE) and brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC) [11][12] [13]. Understanding these parameters is crucial for evaluating the viability of biofuels in internal combustion engines. In this work biodiesel derived

from Jatropha oil and its blend with waste derived fuel has been considered as alternative to diesel fuel.

The core of the biodiesel production process is transesterification, which involves the following steps:

- **Mixing:** The feedstock is mixed with an alcohol (usually methanol or ethanol) and a catalyst (commonly sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide).
- **Reaction:** The mixture is heated and stirred, allowing the triglycerides in the feedstock to react with the alcohol. This reaction produces fatty acid methyl esters (biodiesel) and glycerol.
- **Separation:** After the reaction, the mixture separates into two layers: biodiesel (top layer) and glycerol (bottom layer).

3. Experimentation

One method to address the issue of scrap tires is through biological processing or recycling. Thermochemical conversion plants can be used to turn these used tires into carbon material and energy. JME and TPO, the test fuels, were sourced from a commercial enterprise. A single-cylinder diesel engine with a maximum power productivity of 4.4 kW was used for the research. The experimental setup layout is depicted in figure 2. In order to obtain a baseline analysis, diesel was used for the first set of tests, followed by the JMETPO20 blend. After that, the engine ran with the blend at various preheating temperatures. Diesel was used to start the experiments, and once the engine had warmed up, it was switched to JME and finally the JMETPO20 blend at the initial injection timing of 23 °CA bTDC (as specified by the engine manufacturer) in order to collect reference data. Additionally, experiments with the JMETPO20 blend were carried out at various injection timings. By adding or removing shims, the number of shims installed beneath the pump's plunger was changed, changing the initial injection timing. A probe inserted into the engines' exhaust was used to measure the emissions of HC, CO, O₂, and NO using a AVL instruments gas analyzer. A type-K thermocouple coupled to an Energy combustion analyzer was used to measure the exhaust temperature. Using a 2000 ml fuel reservoir set on a 5000 gm Ohaus digital balance, fuel consumption was calculated. A digital stop watch was used to measure the amount of time that had passed. The standard operating procedure for all runs was to put the engine under the desired load for about ten minutes in total, with the exhaust temperature and emissions readings being taken after about eight minutes. Diesel fuel at room temperature was used for the diesel tests.

29.9, and 31.4% for the JMETPO20 blend, P50, P60, and P70, respectively. When two different fuels with different densities and calorific values are blended, the engine's BTE rises with the appropriate term.

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of the set up

4. Brake Thermal Efficiency

Brake thermal efficiency (BTE) is a measure of the efficiency of an engine in converting the heat from fuel into useful work [14]. It is defined as the ratio of the brake power output to the heat input from the fuel. Higher BTE indicates better engine performance and fuel utilization. Generally, shows comparable or slightly higher BTE than petroleum diesel, attributed to its higher cetane number and better combustion characteristics[15]. Brake specific fuel consumption is a measure of the fuel efficiency of an engine, defined as the amount of fuel consumed per unit of power produced. Lower BSFC values indicate better fuel efficiency. Figure 3 illustrates how, at different preheating temperatures, the blend's and diesel's BTE changes with brake power (BP). The BTE is calculated by multiplying the fuel's lower heating value by the power output to mass flow rate ratio [16]. Between all the fuels used in this study, diesel had the highest BTE value, 29.9% at rated BP. At rated BP, it was 29.8, 29.8,

Fig. 3 Load Vs BTE

5. Nitric Oxide (NO)

Nitric oxide is a precursor to nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), which contributes to the formation of ground-level ozone [17]. The impact of biodiesel blends on NO emissions is complex and can vary based on the blend ratio and engine type [18]. Generally, lower NO emissions are observed with biodiesel blends due to the lower combustion temperatures associated with biodiesel. However, some studies report increased NO emissions at higher biodiesel concentrations, suggesting that the combustion characteristics of biodiesel can influence NO formation. It should be mentioned that the majority of vegetable oils have trace amounts of proteins that contain nitrogen [19]. Through combustion, this tiny quantity of nitrogen, in addition to atmospheric nitrogen, produces

additional NOx emissions. This could be one of the reasons why vegetable oils emit more NO than diesel fuel.

Fig. 4 Load Vs NO

6. Hydrocarbon Emission (HC)

The result of incomplete combustion is these emissions. Carbon monoxide is a colorless, odorless gas that is harmful to human health and the environment [20]. Studies have shown that biodiesel blends generally result in lower CO emissions compared to conventional diesel [21]. The oxygen content in biodiesel facilitates more complete combustion, leading to reduced CO formation. However, the extent of CO reduction can vary depending on the biodiesel blend ratio and the engine operating conditions.

Fig.5 Load Vs HC

The incomplete burning of working fuel within the combustion chamber is indicated by the emission of HC. HC emissions for various blends at 75% load for a range of fuel injection temperatures are displayed in Fig. 5. As the preheating temperature increases, the amount of HC emissions decreases. This is because the JME contains oxygen molecules, which promote better combustion within the engine's cylinder. As the blend temperature rises from 50 °C to 70 °C, the HC emission for blend decreases, as seen in figure. Hydrocarbon oxides, including unburned hydrocarbons, are a significant contributor to air pollution and smog formation [22]. Biodiesel blends typically exhibit lower HC emissions due to improved combustion efficiency. The presence of oxygen in biodiesel enhances the oxidation of fuel, resulting in fewer unburned hydrocarbons. However, some studies indicate that higher blends of biodiesel may lead to increased HC emissions under certain conditions, highlighting the need for further research.

7. Smoke Opacity

Smoke opacity is a measure of the particulate matter emitted during combustion, which can affect air quality and visibility [23]. Biodiesel blends have been shown to reduce smoke opacity compared to conventional diesel fuel. The higher cetane number and lower aromatic content of biodiesel contribute to more complete combustion, resulting in lower particulate emissions [24]. However, the reduction in smoke opacity can vary depending on the specific biodiesel blend and engine settings [25].

Fig. 6 Load Vs Smoke Opacity

8. Conclusion

The performance of biofuels in terms of brake thermal efficiency and brake specific fuel consumption varies significantly based on the type of biofuel and the engine configuration. While biofuels present a promising alternative to fossil fuels, ongoing research and development are essential to optimize their performance and integration into existing energy systems. Understanding these performance metrics is crucial for assessing the potential of biofuels in reducing reliance on fossil fuels and achieving sustainability goals. The use of biodiesel blends presents a promising opportunity to reduce harmful emissions such as carbon monoxide, hydrocarbon oxides, nitric oxide, and smoke opacity. While many studies indicate that biodiesel blends can lead to lower emissions compared to conventional diesel, the effects can vary based on blend ratios, engine types, and operating conditions. Continued research is essential to fully understand the implications of biodiesel use and to optimize its application for cleaner combustion and improved air quality.

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